

Analytical Uses of 1,2-Diaminocyclohexane Tetra-acetic Acid (CDTA) : Determination of Eu^{3+} in presence of Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} Polarographically

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The polarographic method is very suitable for the determination of inorganic ions, since so many of them reduce at the dropping mercury electrode, exhibiting well-defined waves. The half-wave potential for Cd^{2+} in noncomplexing supporting electrolytes is about -0.58 V vs. S. C. E.¹ and that of Eu^{3+} is -0.67 V vs. S. C. E.² Thus in a mixture of both, the two waves are not well separated. Further, in a mixture of lead and europium, as lead reduces earlier than europium in noncomplexing supporting electrolytes, Eu^{3+} cannot be determined accurately in presence of lead. In this communication, a method has been discussed for the determination of europium in presence of lead and cadmium, using CDTA.

Europium oxide, 99.9% pure as supplied by Dr. Theodor Schuchardt-GMBH & Co., Germany, was used and converted to perchlorate by repeated evaporation with perchloric acid. The purity was checked by titrating it against standard CDTA solution amperometrically³. Other reagents were of reagent grade purity. Sodium perchlorate was used as a supporting electrolyte and Triton X₁₀₀ as maximum suppressor.

A L.P. 55 Heyrovsky system polarograph was used manually. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m=1.76$ mg./sec. and $t=4.6$ sec. (at -1.0 V vs. S.C.E. in $1.0M$ sodium perchlorate). The H-type cell with agar-agar bridge, saturated with sodium chloride, was used for polarographic measurements. The pH of the solution was measured by a battery-operated Cambridge pH-meter. All the measurements were done at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$, controlled by a Haake type ultra thermostat. Purified nitrogen was passed for deaeration.

Determination of Eu^{3+} in presence of Cd^{2+} .—Since at and above pH 5.0, Cd^{2+} formed nonreducible complex with CDTA⁴ and Eu -CDTA complex⁵ produced well-defined diffusion-controlled reduction wave, Eu^{3+} was determined by the standard comparison method. The results are recorded in Table I.

1. Jain and Gaur, *Austri. J. Chem.*, 1965, 16, 1687.

2. Laitinen and Taebel, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 825.

3. Jain D. S., Ph. D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, Jaipur, 1965.

4. Jain and Gaur, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 759.

5. Jain and Gaur, presented at IIIrd International Congress of Polarography, Southampton, England, July, 1964.

6. Jain and Gaur, *this Journal*, 1965, 42 753.

TABLE I

Eu³⁺=0.025 M. Cd²⁺=0.025 M.

Eu ³⁺ present (ml)	..	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.8
Cd ²⁺ present (ml)	..	0.5	1.0	2.0	2.0
Eu ³⁺ found (ml)	..	1.0	0.8	1.0	0.8

Determination of Eu³⁺ in presence of Pb²⁺.—On account of the difficulty (*vide supra*) in the accurate determination of Eu³⁺ in presence of lead, it was found that when CDTA was added, first Pb formed a nonreducible complex with CDTA (pH 5.0)⁶, whereas Eu-CDTA complex produced well-defined single reduction wave. Thus Eu³⁺ could be determined in presence of Pb²⁺ by the standard comparison method polarographically.

Solutions containing different amounts of Eu³⁺ and Pb²⁺ and excess of CDTA (10mM) in 0.1M potassium nitrate were prepared (pH 6.0) and polarographed. The amount of europium was calculated by the standard comparison method. The results are recorded in Table II.

*TABLE II

Eu³⁺=0.025 M. Pb²⁺=0.025 M.

Eu ³⁺ present (ml)	..	0.8	1.0	1.2	2.0	1.0
Pb ²⁺ present (ml)	..	0.4	0.8	1.0	2.0	2.0
Eu ³⁺ found (ml)	..	0.80	0.98	1.21	2.00	0.98

*The error is about = 2%.

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